

Pre-Registration Data

Title

FISM, Fighting with a Smile: Satirical and Humourist Voices of Resilience from Hindi Speaking Subaltern Subjects and Communities.

Description

The project aims to investigate specific forms, uses and functions of Hindi contemporary humour (*hasya*) and satire (*vyangya*). To do so, it focuses especially on the connection of these “amorphous” (Davies, Illott 2018) and “formless” (Connery, Combe 1995) modes of expression (Harder 2012) to the sociocultural claims raised by marginalized and/or subaltern subjects and communities in India. Much attention is primarily on the forms of humour and satire which have arisen during the last twenty years and which are characterized by the use of Hindi/Hinglish as the medium of expression. In the research the terms marginalized and subaltern refer primarily, but not exclusively, to the Dalits, the Adivasis, the LGBTQIA+ and to discriminated women in India. However, in a more tangential way, the research will also consider the satirical and humourist narratives produced by authors not belonging to the above-mentioned sociocultural categories. Recent contributions reflecting the informative (Dore 2022; Zekavat 2021), therapeutic (Declercq 2021; Dore 2021; Fry 2000; Garrick 2006) and sociocultural functions (Caron 2021; Chilana, Bhargava 2022; 2024) incorporated by satire and humour, have stressed on the potentiality of these modes to be used as coping strategies also by marginalized and discriminated authors (Shivaprasad 2020; 2021; 2022). In view of the above, the main objective of the research is to shed light on the satirical and humorous narratives pursued by marginalized actors operating in the Hindi literary and extra-literary spheres.

It also interrogates the contribution of Hindi satirists and humourists to specific sociocultural initiatives whose aim is to empower the status of the above-mentioned subjects and communities. Finally, the research investigates personal and collective forms of resilience pursued by humourists and satirists in India. To achieve these set goals, the project surveys, in an interdisciplinary way, many fields in which satire and humour can be detected. Primarily, it focuses on the use of satire in Hindi contemporary literature. Secondly, it investigates ‘life’ beyond literature of humour and satire. To do so, it focuses primarily on the performative uses of satire and humour by Hindi stand-up comedians. Apart from the contribution from authors engaging with this ‘glocal’ form of satire and humour, the research aims to investigate local arts and performative activities related to the modes of humour and satire. From this perspective, the research will also investigate the contribution of the *Hasya kavi sammelans* (Meetings of Humourist poets) to the development of the above-mentioned functions and strategies. Finally, in a more

marginal way, the research will also outline the uses of satire and humour on new media, with emphasis on the role currently played by these in the articulation of sociocultural claims and initiatives by marginalized authors. Analysis of social media also opens up new perspectives on their impact on the humourist and satirical narratives currently embraced by authors in the literary and extra-literary fields.

The project, which has received funding by the European Union under the call Horizon-MSCA-2023-PF-01, will be hosted at Sapienza, University of Rome; it entails a stay of two years in India, where the PI will be affiliated with UPES, University of Dehradun.

Contributors

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Institutions

Sapienza, University of Rome (Italy).

Upes, Dehradun (India).

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Funding:

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Study Information

Research Aims and Objectives

In the light of the above-description, the main *theoretical objectives* of the research are:

1. To shed light on narratives of marginalized satirists/humourists within the Hindi public sphere;
2. To analyse the role of Hindi satire and humour in the articulation of socio-cultural claims and initiatives to empower the status of marginalized authors in India;
3. To analyse the strategies of personal and collective resilience and coping by authors adopting Hindi humour and satire;
4. To investigate the criteria which regulate the access of marginalized authors to performative satirical events.

The main theoretical objectives will be obtained through the achievement of the *following main results*:

1. The textual analysis of at least five books (prose and poetry) written by Hindi literary authors, specialized in the field of satire and humour. The analysis will focus especially on the sections which are more relevant for the scopes of the project.
2. The participation and subsequent textual analysis of at least four stand-up comedy shows and one *Hasya kavi sammelan/Mushayra* focusing on the contribution by marginalized authors;
3. The study and textual analysis and classification of at least four hundred Hindi items, detected from social media, which reveal the digital use of satire and humour by marginalized groups;
4. The realization of five interviews with satirists;
5. The organization of a conference on satire and humour with the participation of international scholars and artists;
6. The publication of three articles on Internationally recognized journals and other dissemination activities;
7. The organization of different activities devoted to the communication of the finalities of the research. Among them, the project entails the realization of a Website and the participation in activities (for example the participation in festivals and events for the larger public) to enhance the impact of the research on the scientific and public audience.
8. The participation in different training activities for the acquisition of methods and knowledge.

To make the specific objectives realistically achievable, the project will rely on the support given by the host, and associated institutions, in establishing contacts with contemporary satirists, journalists, scholars and institutions. Furthermore, to make the progress of the research measurable and reliable, different reports providing all the necessary information to effectively monitor the development will be sent to the European Commission.

Research questions

Previous studies reveal that, while some women literary authors and performers use comedy in the Hindi language to enact the dynamics of empowering the status of women in India (Bhargava, Chilana 2022), generally the relationship of satire/humour with the claims of the Dalit, Adivasi and the LGBTQIA+ groups is ambiguous and problematic (Shivaprasad 2020; Shivaprasad 2021, Shivaprasad 2022). Some Hindi satirists and humourists have portrayed in the past the status of discrimination and marginalization suffered by these communities. However, very few marginalized authors have used these tools to articulate their socio-cultural demands in the contemporary context. In this

research there will be an attempt to investigate the reasons behind this paradoxical situation. Furthermore, an attempt will be made to select narratives of resilience from authors who have been usually placed at the margins of Indian sociocultural environment. In the light of the above, the realization of the research aims and activities starts from a set of basic research questions:

1. If satire and humour are two interdisciplinary modes (Harder 2012), which are the cultural fields and areas belonging to the contemporary “Hindi public sphere” (Orsini 2002) which contribute mostly to the articulation of satirical and humourist narratives of marginalization?
2. Satire, according to Knight (2009), is a mode characterized by an “elitarian frame of mind”. Nevertheless, these modes are currently also being used in different global contexts by marginalized subjects and groups with the scope of raising different sociocultural claims and establishing “reverse discourses” (Caron 2021). In this light, which contribution is offered by marginalized groups and subjects in India to the articulation of new counter and reverse discourses in the Hindi public sphere?
3. Which forms of “satirical activism” (Caron 2021) are currently being used by authors embracing forms of humour and satire?
4. Are humour and satire also used by marginalized groups and subjects to cope with subjective and collective stress and trauma experiences?

In parallel, the research aims to answer a set of secondary questions:

1. How does Hindi literature contribute to the development of satirical and humourist narratives by performative arts?
2. How global performative activities such as stand-up comedy contribute to the raise of narratives of marginalization by authors using Hindi and/or Hinglish as their medium of expression?
3. What possibilities for participation in events such as the *Hasya kavi sammelan/Mushayras* are offered to authors coming from marginalized sections of Indian society?
4. What contribution to the articulation of satirical and humourist narratives by marginalized authors is offered by the rise of new social media/social networks?
5. Which are the ‘mediatic’ uses of satire and humour in Hindi/Hinglish?
6. How have the arts of humour and satire changed in India over the last few years under the push of new global satirical tendencies? How are these changes affecting Indian public opinion?

Anticipated Duration

The project commencement date is 01/07/2024 and the completion date will be 01/07/2027.

Design Plan

Study design

The project work plan consists of different activities:

1. "Preliminary Analysis of sources" will involve the preliminary analysis of the literary and extra-literary sources of the project.
2. "Participant observation and Textual Analysis" will involve the participant's observation at performative events characterized by the use of humour and satire. It will consist in attending stand-up comedy shows by authors using Hindi or Hinglish as a linguistic medium; this work-package will also cover the *Hasya kavi sammelans* and other performative events characterized by the adoption of humour and satire as modes of expression.
3. "Textual Analysis of Hindi satirical literature" will be the qualitative textual analysis of literary texts which reveal the use of satire and humour. It will cover the study of selected Hindi prose and poetry production, with a focus on the literary works produced by Dalit, Adivasi and women writers. In a more marginal way, the project also entails the investigation of satirical and humourist texts published in Hindi literary magazines and journals.
4. "Textual analysis of comedy-related sources on social-media and networks" will consist of the textual analysis of materials characterized by the use of humour and satire and published on social media.
5. "Interview"; the project entails the realization of interviews with artists and scholars.
6. "Focus Group"; the project entails the realization of a focus group.
7. "Dissemination" will be pursued through the publication of the results of the research in open-access journals; it will involve participating in at least two conferences and one workshop and organizing a conference.
8. "Communication and public engagement"; different activities will be realized during the project with the scope of communicating the results of the project to the larger audience. Primarily, the project entails the creation and use of a website, which will be used as a platform to inform the public about the objectives of the project. The PI will also deliver at least four speeches to the public.

Sampling and case selection strategy

1. All the literary and extra-literary sources which are subject to textual analysis are chosen on the basis of their adherence to the main theoretical objectives of the research. In particular, all the selected texts reveal the use of humour and satire and are characterized by the use of Hindi and/or Hinglish as the linguistic medium of

expression. Moreover, the majority of the selected texts are produced by authors belonging to the above-mentioned marginalized sociocultural communities.

2. The recruitment criterium used in the collection of data provided by the interviews and the focus group will be based on the snowball strategy. All the activities will cover the participation of researchers, activists and performers connected to the field of satire and humour. In all the phases, the research will respect the criterium of gender equality.

Data Collection

Data source(s) and data type(s)

Data prior to the study:

- Secondary literature on satire and humour in India. The materials will be in Hindi and in other languages.
- Hindi newspaper and magazine articles.
- Archival data from private collections and public libraries in India.
- Hindi literary sources.
- Videos of stand-up comedy shows and Hasya kavi sammelans uploaded on social media.
- Social media materials.
- Data collected for different purposes from the current study and published in previous articles.

Data collected or generated during the study:

- Reports produced during the project.
- Data analysis of the literary sources.
- Data analysis of the performative sources.
- Data analysis of the social media sources.
- Observations produced during participant observation at performative events.
- Audiovisual recordings produced during the project.
- Notes and observations produced during the project.
- Interviews produced during the project.
- Written or audiovisual recordings of the sessions of the focus group.
- Consent forms.
- Metadata.
- Articles.
- Presentations during seminars.
- Proceedings of dissemination and communication activities.
- Posters.

- A Website.

Data collection methods

1. "Interview": used to gather information from scholars and artists. It will also be used to gather information in a collective and anonymous way from the audience at the performative activities.
1. "Focus group": used in the research to gather information from scholars and artists; it will also facilitate the organization of communication and dissemination of the activities which entail the participation of stakeholders.
2. "Archival research": used to analyze archival data from public libraries and private collections.
3. "Participative observation"; to gather observations from performative shows and events.
4. "Notes and observations"; the notes are used to collect data during the phase of training at the host and affiliated institutions. Moreover, they will be used to collect data from the study of primary and secondary literature.
5. "Audiovisual recording"; the recording is used to audiovisually record the interviews, the performative activities and the sessions of the focus group.
6. "Textual Analysis"; the textual analysis will be used to analyse and collect data prior to the study or generated during the research. The project implies different kinds of textual analysis: textual analysis of Hindi literary texts; analysis of recorded or pre-existing performative texts; analysis of data derived from social media.

Data collection tools, instruments or plans

The collection of the data will entail the use of the following tools, instruments:

1. A secure cloud storage to remotely store all the different kinds of data (See section 6.2.).
2. An Open Data platform will be used to deposit all the data generated during the research (See section 6.2.). The Open Data platform will use the data in compliance with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).
3. A personal computer at the host and/or at the affiliated institutions, where all the data collected and generated are stored in a secure and private way.
4. Legal consents, which, in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, n. 2016/679), regulate the use of personal data by participants. Legal consents will display all the rights and responsibilities of the participants; as well as the research aims and criteria for data collection and handling.
5. A video camera, used to audiovisually record the interviews and the performative activities related to the finalities of the project.

6. Several reports will be generated throughout the project to prove the development of the research and the achievement of the theoretical objectives, results and work packages of the research.
7. An AI software to facilitate the transcription of audiovisual texts.
8. A Data Management Plan (DPM), to be generated by the 6th month of the project. The Data Management Plan describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by a European-funded project. The DPM will include: information on the handling of research data during and after the end of the project; what data will be collected, generated and processed; which methodology and standards will be applied; whether data will be shared in open access; the measures taken to protect and secure data. The DPM will be updated during the research whenever significant changes arise with regards to the use of the collected and generated data.

Stopping criteria

The following rationales used by the researcher to stop data generation or collection:

1. “Data saturation”; this rationale implies that the data generation will stop when the collected data is sufficient to satisfy the theoretical objectives and results of the research. The research will follow the perspective for which saturation is reached when there is enough information to replicate the study.
2. “Resource constraints”; this rationale implies that the collection of data will be conducted respecting the time limits as envisaged by the research timeline.

Analysis Plan

The research will be interdisciplinary and based mainly on qualitative methods:

- Pure qualitative methods will be used for the textual analysis of the literary sources. The method used for the critical analysis of the texts will adopt – but not be limited to – the Simpson’s model (2003). It is an integrated stylistic method considering four variables: setting, method, uptake and target— SMUT.
- Another pure qualitative method will consist in interviewing some of the main actors in the field of Hindi satire. These interviews will be pursued through unstructured questions made online or in-person modality. The selection of the participants will be pursued by respecting the criteria of a gender balanced representation. One approach that will be used is based on the Braun and Clarke model (2006), characterized by the coding and the further thematization of the concepts expressed by the authors in their interviews.

- With regards to the analysis of the performative life of Hindi satire, the project includes the adoption of qualitative models specifically designed for ethnographic studies. A balanced positioning will allow a combination of involvement and necessary detachment from the object of investigation. The Textual Analysis of the texts will be based on a semantic approach to the study of satirical texts.
- 4. Mixed qualitative and quantitative methods will be applied to the study of social media and networks.

Credibility strategies

- Throughout the project different measures will be employed to assure methodological integrity:
- Dialogue with international scholars during any phase of the research. More in particular, the PI will be supported by scholars at the host and affiliated institution. Moreover, the activities of the PI will be continuously monitored and checked by the supervisors at Sapienza and at UPES.
- Dialogue with an ethics mentor, who will advise the PI in the realization of the Data Management Plan and other deliverables concerning the handling of the ethics aspects in the research.
- Consensus among subjects.
- Dialogue with subjects in any phase of the research.
- The respect of the FAIR principles in the collection and generation of data.
- Triangulation with other data sources related to the theoretical objectives of the research.
- Negative case analysis.
- Reflexivity.

Dialogue with experts will be essential to check the progress of the research and to advise the PI on the implementation of the methodology and methods to produce research outputs. Moreover, this dialogue will be crucial, allowing collaboration in activities regarding the dissemination and communication of the results. The ethics mentor will also be necessary in advising the PI on matters concerning the compliance of the project with the ethical regulations of the European Commission. By doing so, the ethics mentor will also advise the PI during the realization of the Data Management Plan, which is expected to be produced by the sixth month of the

research. Dialogue with people (mostly writers and artists) will be necessary in order to create consensus among subjects with regards to the measures adopted by the PI to produce different kinds of data. The dialogue, for example, will be necessary whenever the PI tells the subjects to collect and analyse data derived from interviews, performative activities and the focus group. Other measures, such as triangulation with other data sources, negative case analysis and reflexivity will be necessary in order to validate the quality of the research.